

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS OF SCHOOL DISBURSING OFFICERS AND LIQUIDATORS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 8

Pages: 939-949

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1813

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11182858

Manuscript Accepted: 04-09-2024

Challenges and Coping Mechanisms of School Disbursing Officers and Liquidators

Lalaine D. Jacob,* Vilma H. Arazo

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study determined the challenges and coping mechanisms of school Disbursing officers and liquidators for the school year 2022-2023. The study was conducted in the 1st quarter of 2022-2023. The study utilized the descriptive-correlation research design to test the significant relationship between the respondents' challenges, coping mechanisms, and the profile; and which variable best predicts the dependent variable. The respondents were the twelve Disbursing Officers and school liquidators at the elementary level. Most of the respondents were 32 – 39 years old, female, married, with business courses, had rendered services for 8 years and above, and were assigned in the coastal area. In the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of personal challenges, the result showed that the respondents had an overall score of 3.33 with a description of “Strongly Agree”. While in the work-related challenges, the result showed a 3.26 weighted mean in the respondents with a description of “Strongly Agree”. The null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the coping mechanisms and the challenges encountered by the respondents, was rejected. Furthermore, in regression analysis, the respondents' coping mechanism was affected by work-related challenges. This implied that work-related challenges were the only predictor that affects the respondents' coping mechanism. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' coping mechanism” was not rejected.

Keywords: *challenges, coping mechanism, disbursing officers, school liquidators*

Introduction

Working in the field of finance especially in preparing the liquidation report is somehow a challenging task. Commission on Audit (COA) issued a Circular Number 97-002, Restatement with amendments of the rules and regulations on the granting, utilization and liquidation of cash advances provided for under COA Circular No. 90-331 dated May 3, 1990. It is strictly implemented the on - time submission of liquidation report as requisite for the next cash advance of the following month or quarter. So, to submit it promptly, the Disbursing Officer helped both in canvassing and procuring of goods especially if the technical working group are not available due to no disruption of classes.

Transactions of Fifty Thousand (50,000.00) and above is subject for posting in the Philippine Government Electronic Procurement System (PhilGEPS). It is an online portal where government agencies post their procurement requirements. It was created to automate the purchasing procedure, remove any doubt, and guarantee transparency in government contracts. Disbursing officer will be the one to post and upload request for quotation to be filled out by the interested bidder. Closing date will be 7 calendar days after posting and it will automatically close. After the closing date, the Disbursing Officer will check the email and print the quotations uploaded by the interested bidders and give it to the Bids and Award Committee for the purpose of determining the lowest bidder at the same time can provide the best quality of goods and services. In posting the online portal, Philippine Government Electronic Procurement System (PhilGEPS), we need a strong internet connection so that we can transact it smoothly without any delay.

These challenges may affect its promptness in submission of liquidation report and will create another problem. Circular Number 97-002, Restatement with amendments of within the station and three (3) months for officer outside the station from date of grant of the cash advance, the Auditor shall issue a letter demanding liquidation or explanation for non-liquidation. And worst, the officer shall likewise be held criminally liable, for failure to settle his accounts after the given time. The rules and regulations on the granting, utilization and liquidation of cash advances provided for under COA Circular No. 90-331 dated May 3, 1990, stated that upon the officer refusal to repay his monetary advance within two (2) months for officer holding office.

Furthermore, the procurement process needs a thorough review in accordance with the Procurement Act, Republic Act 9184. As Disbursing Officer in the Elementary school, there were challenges encountered in order to function well in accordance with the law. The procedures and processes itself sometimes can cause the delay of the transactions. Procurement process starts with canvassing to be done by a school Canvassers. Sometimes if they are not around, Disbursing Officer will be the one to canvass to fast track the transaction even if we know our part that it is against in R. A. 9184. After canvassing, the winning bidder will be awarded by the Bids and Awards Committee (BAC) and purchase order will follow. Purchase order to be signed by the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE) and to be received by the winning supplier as serve as the bind contract between the two contracting parties.

Further, the purchase order should be received by the office of the Commission on Audit (COA) for verification before purchasing the item. The Disbursing Officer then now issue a check and prepared Advice of Check Issued and Cancelled (ACIC) and will do the payment procedure. Once the items were paid and procured, the Disbursing Officer will schedule an appointment from the COA office for an inspection of goods based on the purchase order submitted in their office. The Inspectorate together with the COA Personnel will check the goods as to quantity, quality, and its price before releasing it to the end users.

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered by the school disbursing officers and liquidators and their coping mechanisms for the school year 2022-2023. The study was conducted in the 2nd quarter of 2022-2023. The researcher is 5 years in service and has an eagerness to make appropriate adjustments to be more effective and efficient in her career by trying a humble process in the preparation of liquidation report.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the challenges encountered by the school disbursing officers and liquidators and their coping mechanisms for the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions;

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of;
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 marital status;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.5 location of work assignment?
2. What are the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 personal challenges; and
 - 2.2 work –related challenges?
3. What are the coping mechanisms employed by the respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and coping mechanisms?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges and the coping mechanisms employed by the respondents?
6. What action plan can be formulated based on the results of the study?

Methodology

This section deals with the methods and procedures in gathering data for the study. This includes the research design, research environment, respondents of the study, research instrument, data gathering procedures and statistical tools used.

Research Design

The study used the descriptive-correlational research design in as much as this study described the age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, location of work assignment, challenges, and coping mechanisms. It was also correlation research since the demographic profile of the respondents was correlated to the challenges and coping mechanisms of Disbursing Officers and school liquidators in the elementary schools in the Division of Iligan City.

Participants

The respondents were eleven (11) Disbursing officers and ninety-five 95 school liquidators. There were 22 male and 84 female in the total of ninety - six (96). The researcher used the complete enumeration due to limited disbursing officers in the school. Before the researcher visited to the central schools where the disbursing officers situated, the researcher informed the respondents about the schedule before handed personally including the survey forms intended to the school liquidator since they were always visited to their disbursing officers for the check issuance and for their liquidation report matters.

Table 1. *Number of Disbursing Officers and BAC Members*

District	Number of Disbursing Officers	Number of Bids and Awards Committee (BAC Secretariat/school liquidators)
East I	1	10
East II	1	8
North I	1	14
North II	1	15
North III	1	15
South I	1	8
South II	1	8
West I	1	6
West II	1	6
City Central	2	5
Total	11	95
Over-All Total		106

Instruments

This study utilized a researcher-made instrument to validate the proper utilization of school Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) with regards to the procurement procedures stipulated in the Procurement Act also known as the Republic Act 9184. The survey questionnaire was composed of 50 items and answered through checking the corresponding number based on their level of application or satisfaction. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for correction before it was administered. The questionnaire underwent pilot testing at Iligan City National High School, Iligan City National High School – Annex, Iligan City School of Fisheries, Tipanoy, National High School - Annex, Maria Cristina National High School, Kiwalan National High School, Digkilaan National High School and Tomas Cabili National High School to test the internal consistency of the of the statements/indicators.

Table 2. *Reliability Analysis of Variables*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Number of Questions</i>	<i>Cronbach Alpha</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Challenges Encountered			
Personal Challenges	14	0.873	Reliable
Work-related Challenges	26	0.810	Reliable
Coping Mechanisms	10	0.903	Reliable

Table 2 presents the reliability analysis of variables. The result shows that the questionnaire consisted of 50 questions composed of the challenges encountered in terms of personal challenges with a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.873; work-related challenges with 0.810; and the coping mechanisms with 0.903, which indicated that all questions were reliable. The threshold value in the literature is much higher than 0.700. This implied that the participating respondents clearly understood the research questions, and similar questions are answered in the same direction.

Procedure

The usual research protocol was adhered to in the conduct of this research study. This meant that appropriate communications were sent prior to the actual data gathering activity. Once the communications were approved, the data gathering commence.

The researcher visited first the districts located in the hinterland which were the East I and East II districts going down to the coastal areas, North II, North III, South I, South II, West I, West II and City Central District respectively. The researcher explained the survey questionnaire to the Disbursing Officers and the school liquidators as the respondents of the study.

After one week, the researcher followed up the survey questionnaire and visited the districts located in the coastal area. Those districts located in the hinterland, the researcher retrieved the questionnaires through sending messages thru messenger and short message service (sms) with the help of the disbursing officers assigned in those districts. The retrieval of the survey questionnaire took two weeks until it was completed and gathered as to the targeted number of respondents.

The result of the survey was tallied and submitted to the accredited statistician of the school for the analysis data.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems.

For problem 1, Frequency and Percentage were used in analyzing the profile of the respondents as to age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment and location of work assignment.

For problem 2, Mean, and Standard deviation were used to determine the challenges encountered of the respondents in terms of personal and work - related challenges and coping mechanisms.

For problem 3, the Chi – Squared test was used to determine the relationship between the demographic profile and the challenges encountered.

For problem 4, Spearman Correlation was used to determine the relationship between the coping mechanisms and the challenges of the respondents.

For problem 5, Regression was used to correlate between the coping mechanism, challenges encountered, and profile; and to determine the best predictor variable/s.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, course, length of service, and location of work assignment?

Table 3. Age of the Respondents

Age (in Years Old)	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
23 – 31	26	24.5
32 – 39	31	29.2
40 – 47	29	27.4
48 - 55	15	14.2
56 - 63	5	4.7
Total	106	100.0

Table 3 presents the age of the respondents. The result showed that a very high number of the respondents were of the ages between thirty - two (32) to thirty - nine (39) denoted by a frequency of 31 or 29.2%. This meant that the majority of the respondents were thirty - two (32) to thirty - nine (39) years old, belonging to the millennial generation and able to work competitively because they are computer savvy where they can foster innovation and creativity in the organization that lead to numerous benefits and positive consequences on employee's psychology, behavior and performance, through influence the competitive performance of the organization and affects positively on financial performance (Nguyen and Le, 2019).

Table 4. Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
Male	22	20.8
Female	84	79.2
Total	106	100.0

Table 4 displays the sex of the respondents. The result presented that the number of females outnumbered the number of males. As noticed in the table, eighty - four (84) out of one hundred six (106) or 79.2% of female which were 22 or 89.04% higher than the number of male respondents. These findings connoted that in the existing school system composed of ten (10) districts and ninety - five (95) responding schools, the number of female Disbursing Officers and school liquidators was higher than the male Disbursing Officers and school liquidators. This connotation gave a view that the heavier bulk of the perceptions in this study generated from the female respondents (Regalado, 2018).

Table 5 displays the marital status of the respondents. The result presented depicts the domination of married personnel in the department which was 62 or 58.5%. The prevalence of married Disbursing Officers and school liquidators could mean that civil status may be considered as one of the factors for getting hired in the institution.

Having a spouse, had its benefits as well because they contributed more manpower to upkeep, improvement, and more connections that may benefit the administration, teachers and learners. Working together to achieve common objectives and willing to commit all their energies necessary to ensure the objectives are achieved (Humphries, 2022).

Table 5. Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
Single	40	37.7
Married	62	58.5
Separated	2	1.9
Widowed	2	1.9
Total	106	100.0

Table 6. Educational Attainment of the Respondents

Course	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
Business	43	40.6
Education	41	38.7
Engineering	4	3.8
Formal Science	5	4.7
Humanities	2	1.9
Natural Science	4	3.8
Public Administration	5	4.7
Social Science	2	1.9
Total	106	100.0

Table 6 displays the educational attainment of the respondents. The result presented that among the eight (8) courses presented in the table above, most of the respondents took up course related to business with 43 or 45.58% compared to other courses. It revealed that the respondents had a background related to financial matters which is relevant to their current functions in their respective district or school as Disbursing Officers and school liquidators.

Nowadays, as we are living in a rapid changing, high and low economic status, we should at least know the ability to understand, analyze, manage, and communicate finance matters (Vitt, 2015).

Table 7. Length of Service of the Respondents

Length of Service	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
1 year and below	11	10.4
2-3 years	26	24.5
4-5 years	25	23.6
6-7 years	15	14.2
8 years and above	29	27.4
Total	106	100.0

Table 7 shows the respondents' length of service. The result revealed that the highest distribution of the length of service fall into 8 years and above with 29 or 27.4%. It implied that the respondents were effective, competent and had a commendable work performance because of their level of experience.

According to Motowidlo (2018), task performance is the level of effectiveness with which job incumbents perform activities that contribute to the organization's technical core.

Table 8 displays the respondents' work locations. The result presented that there were outnumbered respondents assigned in the coastal area with 73 or 68.9% compared to hinterland area. This simply means that there were also outnumbered schools situated in coastal area compared to hinterland area. Teachers rendered 2 - 3 years above assigned in the hinterland wanted to transfer in the schools located in the coastal area preferably near to their residences so that they can fully maximize their time and be able to share their expertise that could greatly help to boost not only for themselves but for the organization as well.

Teamwork, collaboration, and trust are the missing pieces needed to complete the high - performing organization puzzle (Katz & Miller, 2023).

Table 8. Respondents' Work Locations

Work Locations	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
Coastal Area	73	68.9
Hinterland Area	33	31.1
Total	106	100.0

Problem 2: What are the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of personal challenges and work-related challenges?

Table 9 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of personal challenges. The result showed that the respondents had an average of 3.33 on their challenges encountered, that depicted as "Strongly Agree". Most of the respondents preferably choose "Strongly Agree" as their response in each indicator. Indicator number 1 which is, adopt new techniques to smoothen and fast tract every transaction got the highest mean with 3.49. It connoted that in the education system, there were rapid changing in the procedures and processes implemented by the higher authority, that's for standardization that were beneficial not only to the employee but for the whole agency as a whole.

Table 9. Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in terms of Personal Challenges

Indicators	Mean	±	SD	Description
Difficulties in adopting new techniques to smoothen and fast tract every transaction.	3.49	±	0.70	Strongly Agree
Hesitant to ask colleagues who is more knowledgeable to the work.	1.98	±	0.87	Disagree
Encountered challenges to work in a team rather than working with alone.	3.26	±	0.76	Strongly Agree
Not interested in brainstorming with regards to the improvement of work performance.	3.43	±	0.70	Strongly Agree
Cannot cope up personal problems that may affect the work performance.	3.21	±	0.80	Agree
Lack support from the school head and colleagues in terms of systematic procedures implemented.	3.39	±	0.71	Strongly Agree
Cannot find effective ways to minimize unavoidable mistakes.	3.47	±	0.71	Strongly Agree
Difficulties in Handling stress due to workloads.	3.31	±	0.64	Strongly Agree
Difficulties in Coping with the deadline of submission of liquidation report.	3.36	±	0.73	Strongly Agree
Cannot study and learn to improve work performance.	3.57	±	0.57	Strongly Agree
Cannot remain calm and effective especially in meeting the deadlines set by the Division Office.	3.70	±	2.94	Strongly Agree
Difficulties in dealing with the clients especially the school heads, teachers, learners and stakeholders.	3.48	±	0.73	Strongly Agree
Difficulties in adopting changes and techniques to fast tract every transaction.	3.45	±	0.68	Strongly Agree
Hesitant to suggest new innovative ideas for the improvement of the liquidation process,	3.54	±	3.08	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.33	±	0.54	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

The respondents were having a difficulty in embracing the new policies due to workloads and meeting the deadlines in submission of reports. Indicator number 2, hesitant to ask colleagues who is more knowledgeable to work got the description of Disagree. Of all the respondents, only one respondent chose the description of disagree. It means that the respondent answered this number was open minded, eager to improved his work by soliciting brilliant and innovative ideas from his colleagues to make his performance effective. He believes that working collaboratively will result into a productive one. Individuals differ in innumerable ways, some adaptive, some maladaptive, and some neutral (Buss and Greiling, 2018).

In this study, most of the respondents were challenged and not yet ready to grasp the ever-changing system implemented in the organization. They were supposedly and should be able to adopt the technological advancements relevant to their work. According to Gould, 2018, “tech savvies” who contribute to the life sciences via their knowledge and skills rather than expertise.

Table 10 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of work-related challenges. The result showed a 3.26 weighted mean in the respondents in terms of work - related challenges with the description of “Strongly Agree”. Indicator number 16 which was, late to prepare purchase request from the end users and processed the approval from the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE) got the highest mean which is 4.44. It connoted that the Disbursing Officers and school liquidators considered this indicator as the most challenging task they had. They strictly followed the Republic Act 9184 also known as the “Government Procurement Act” even if it directly affects the procurement process. Before the procurement of a particular goods or services, the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE) or the school Principal must see to it that the pprocurement shall be in accordance with the approved Annual Procurement Plan (APP) of the Procuring Entity. The Annual Procurement Plan (APP) shall be approved by the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE) and must be consistent with its duly approved yearly budget.

Table 10. *Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in terms of Work-related Challenges*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Difficulty to cater two or more schools or with 3 or more teaching loads	2.57	±	1.17	Agree
Cannot performed tasks not indicated in the Key Result Areas (KRA).	3.06	±	0.91	Agree
Inadequate training and seminars attended related to the job.	2.93	±	0.84	Agree
Late in Preparing Annual Procurement Plan – Common Use Supplies and Equipment (APP-CSE), Project Procurement Management Plan (PPMP) and School Operating Budget (SOB).	2.93	±	1.02	Agree
Difficulty in posting request for quotation (RFQ) in every procurement that reach 50,000.00 and above through the Philippine Government Electronic Procurement System.	2.92	±	0.98	Agree
Difficulty in awarding the winning bidder of the procurement above 50,000.00 and above through the Philippine Government Electronic Procurement System.	3.20	±	2.09	Agree
Cannot do canvassing if the Technical Working Group (TWG) or Canvassers are not available.	3.28	±	1.10	Strongly Agree
Cannot serve purchase orders to the suppliers approved by the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE) or the school Principal.	3.15	±	0.91	Agree
Late to submit purchase orders to the Commission on Audit (COA) office for verification before purchasing the goods.	3.11	±	0.98	Agree
Difficulty in issuing check to the approved purchase orders with approved disbursement vouchers, three (3) sets of accomplished canvass forms, abstract of proposals for furnishing of supplies and materials, resolution to award, notice to award and certificate of creditable tax withheld at source.	3.08	±	1.11	Agree
Difficulty in purchasing goods and services.	3.16	±	0.87	Agree
Late to prepare Program of Works with quarterly School Operating Budget (SOB).	3.18	±	0.77	Agree
Late to update the Check Disbursement Record of the purchases incurred monthly.	3.10	±	0.98	Agree
Difficulty in maintaining the filing system for easy access especially if there is a random inspection from the Commission on Audit personnel.	3.39	±	0.78	Strongly Agree
Failed to coordinate with the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE) for the purchases needed.	3.43	±	0.74	Strongly Agree
Late to prepare purchase request from the end users and processed the approval from the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE).	4.44	±	0.74	Strongly Agree
Unable to delegate the canvassing to the Technical Working Group (TWG) like the school Canvassers.	3.28	±	0.96	Strongly Agree
Failed to prepare canvass forms in three copies with three participating bidders and should check it properly with regards to the supplier’s basic information like tax identification number, vat or non-VAT and their signatures.	4.18	±	1.01	Strongly Agree
Difficulty in checking the completeness of the documents of the winning bidder like business permit and Philippine Government Electronic Procurement System (PhilGeps).	3.48	±	0.01	Strongly Agree
Late to prepare purchase order and seek the approval of the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE).	3.31	±	0.89	Strongly Agree
Late in preparing disbursement voucher and other documents needed for the purchase of goods and services.	3.31	±	0.87	Strongly Agree
Late to prepare check disbursement registry and monthly alpha list.	3.28	±	0.94	Strongly Agree
Late in facilitating the Commission on Audit personnel for the inspection of goods purchased.	3.28	±	1.07	Strongly Agree
Difficulty in preparing two sets of liquidation reports. One for the Commission on Audit (COA) copy and one for the School Accounting Unit (SAU) copy.	3.21	±	1.04	Agree
Difficulty to cope with the additional requirements set by the accounting office and COA.	3.34	±	0.79	Strongly Agree
Difficulty to prepare and submit liquidation report on or before the deadline.	3.27	±	0.96	Strongly Agree

Weighted Mean 3.26 ± 0.73 Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

It revealed that this indicator got the highest mean because in the part of the school liquidator, before he/she is going to accept purchase requests from the teachers and other personnel as the end users, he/she must see to it that those goods and services requested were reflected in the Annual Procurement Plan (APP). Most of the teachers requested some items that are not reflected in the said Annual Procurement Plan (APP) that were vital to their teaching – learning process. Unfortunately, in the school liquidators’ level, they already rejected their requests that leads sometimes to misunderstanding and cold war since some of the teachers were not fully aware of the procedures in the procurement process. But in the end, they were able to cope up and understand the process with the help of the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE) or the school Principal.

Conflict may be managed by (1) joint decision making; (2) third-party decision making; or (3) separate action, including unilateral behaviors such as retreat, withdrawal, and tacit coordination (Pruitt & Carnevale, 1993).

Problem 3: What are the coping mechanisms employed by the respondents?

Table 11 presents the coping mechanisms employed by the respondents. The result showed a 3.40 weighted mean in terms of the respondents’ coping mechanism with description of: Strongly Agree”. Indicator number 5 which stated, I seek help from the District/ Division Office when I have doubts about liquidation, with 3.54 highest mean. It implied that respondents were fully aware that government procurement must not be taken for granted. There were unavoidable instances during the procurement but it must be reported honestly to the Division Accountant or to the Commission on Audit (COA) especially in granting, utilization and liquidation of cash advances for school Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) (COA Circular No. 90-331, May, 1990). This department or agency can surely give correct procedures on how to properly disbursed the government fund without any future dilemma.

Table 11. Respondents’ Coping Mechanism

Indicators	Mean	±	SD	Description
1.I spend time trying to understand what happened.	3.46	±	0.72	Strongly Agree
2. I constantly make a follow up to the BAC members and technical working group.	3.33	±	0.78	Strongly Agree
3. I always read memoranda and messages in the group chat for updates.	3.50	±	0.64	Strongly Agree
4. I consider several alternatives in handling the problem.	3.43	±	0.57	Strongly Agree
5. I seek help from the District/ Division Office when I have doubts about liquidation.	3.54	±	0.66	Strongly Agree
6. Delegate the canvassing to the Technical Working Group (TWG) like the school Canvassers.	3.46	±	0.72	Strongly Agree
7. Prepare canvass forms in three copies with three participating bidders and should check it properly with regards to the supplier’s basic information like tax identification number, vat or non-VAT and their signatures.	3.39	±	0.81	Strongly Agree
8. Check the completeness of the documents of the winning bidder like business permit and Philippine Government Electronic Procurement System (PhilGeps).	3.36	±	0.73	Strongly Agree
9. Prepare purchase order and seek the approval of the Head of the Procuring Entity (HOPE).	3.21	±	0.87	Agree
10. Prepare disbursement voucher and other documents needed for the purchase of goods and services.	3.32	±	0.74	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.40	±	0.48	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and coping mechanisms?

Table 12. Respondents’ Efficiency and Promptness in Submission of Liquidation Report and Demographic Profile

Variables	Efficiency and Promptness		Remarks	Decision
	X ² (df)	p-value		
Age	54.608 ^{ns} (60)	0.672	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Sex	18.520 ^{ns} (15)	0.222	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Marital status	42.761 ^{ns} (60)	0.943	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Course	93.533 ^{ns} (105)	0.781	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Length of service	85.632* (60)	0.017	Significant	Reject H ₀
Location of work assignment	29.325* (15)	0.015	Significant	Reject H ₀

Legend: 1 – based on Chi-squared Test ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns – P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

Table 12 displays the relationship between the respondents’ coping mechanisms and the demographic profile. The result showed that the respondents’ coping mechanisms had a highly significant association with their demographic profile in terms of length of service and location of work assignment. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents’ coping mechanisms and the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, marital status, and course were not rejected, while the length of service and location of work assignment were rejected.

The length of service of the employees has something to do with their level of work performance and work efficacy. Those experienced

employees tend to work smoothly and can easily find effective ways that leads to numerous output that indicate progress not only for his/her own growth but the organization as well.

According to Motowidlo, 2018, task performance had something to do with the level of effectiveness with which job incumbents perform activities that contribute to the organization’s technical core.

Location of work assignment also contributed a lot with regards to the respondents’ coping mechanisms because Disbursing Officers and school liquidators who were assigned in the coastal areas can fully maximized their skills because the resources were readily available within their visibility. Aside from that, there were lot of teachers or personnel assigned in the coastal areas who were competent and knowledgeable enough where they can collaborate for additional insights in enriching their goals.

Teamwork, collaboration, and trust are the missing pieces needed to complete the high - performing organization puzzle (Katz & Miller, 2016).

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the challenges and the coping mechanisms employed by the respondents?

Table 13 displays the relationship between the coping mechanisms and the challenges encountered by the respondents. The result showed that the respondents’ coping mechanisms had a significant relationship with the challenges encountered in terms of personal challenges and work-related challenges. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the coping mechanisms and the challenges encountered by the respondents, was rejected.

Table 13. Relationship Respondents’ Coping Mechanism and Challenges Encountered

Variables	Coping Mechanism		Remarks	Decision
	r-value	p-value		
Personal challenges	0.199*	0.041	Significant	Reject H ₀
Work-related challenges	0.281**	0.004	Significant	Reject H ₀

Legend: 1 – based on Chi-squared Test ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns – P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

Coping mechanisms had something to do with respondents’ challenges in terms of personal and work challenges. We are fully aware that in our workplace we met different challenges with regards to our work performance and efficacy. Workloads and meeting the deadlines set by the Division office, for example. Every now and then, there are new implementing rules and regulations to be followed for standardization. We tend to be hesitant at first because it sometimes builds confusions but with those coping mechanisms, respondents were able to cope up and still produce numerous outputs that were commendable.

Personal challenges that were unavoidable sometimes leads to poor performance especially if we were hesitant to ask and solicit insights from other experts or colleagues who were knowledgeable enough to a particular thing.

Therefore, respondents' personal or work challenges must be addressed through different coping mechanisms that are best suited based on their personalities and the kind of environment they had, including their workmates, administrators, and even learners that surrounded them. Lastly, it is very important to note how the respondents respond things in terms of their eagerness to be more work - driven and goal oriented.

Motivation is something that moves the person to action and continues him in the course of action already initiated. Motivation is the willingness to exert high levels of effort towards organizational goals, conditioned by the effort and ability to satisfy some individual need (Roddins 2016).

Problem 6: Which of the demographic profile and challenges encountered best predict coping mechanisms of the respondents?

Table 14. Variables that best predict Respondents’ Coping Mechanism

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.626	0.469		5.601	0.000
Age	-0.024	0.047	-0.056	-0.510	0.612
Sex	-0.028	0.118	-0.024	-0.238	0.812
Marital status	0.080	0.085	0.099	0.938	0.351
Length of service	0.004	0.036	0.010	0.098	0.922
Course	0.033	0.027	0.124	1.258	0.211
Location of work	-0.168	0.101	-0.161	-1.656	0.101
Personal challenges	0.101	0.094	0.113	1.071	0.287
Work-related challenges	0.167	0.067	0.253	2.479	0.015
	R = 0.376	R ² = 0.141	F = 1.950	Sig. = 0.061	

Table 14 presents the variables that best predict respondents’ coping mechanism. The respondents’ coping mechanism was affected by work-related challenges with β = 0.167, t= 2.479, (p<0.015). This implied that work-related challenges were the only predictor that affects the respondents' coping mechanism.

The R2 value of 0.141 implies that 14.1% of the variance in coping mechanisms can be explained by work-related challenges. Hence, 85.9% of the respondents' coping mechanism difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 1.950 with a corresponding p-value of 0.061. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' coping mechanism" was not rejected.

Problem 7: What action plan can be formulated based on the results of the study?

Conclusion

Based on the analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

The study concluded that the personal and work - related challenges greatly affect the job performance of the disbursing officers and school liquidators. Therefore, to address those challenges, there were various coping mechanisms employed in order to continuously perform the duties and responsibilities given. Furthermore, it is also concluded that there was a significant relationship between the coping mechanisms and demographic profile in terms of length of service and location of work assignment as well as coping mechanisms and challenges encountered in terms of personal and work - related challenges.

In light of the findings, the following recommendations are offered: (1) The school administrators must conduct Learning Action Cell (LAC) session on RA 9184 to revisit the procurement processes especially on the matter of requesting items that are not reflected in the Annual Procurement Plan (APP) and Project Procurement Management Plan (PPMP). Although those materials are vital in the teaching – learning process, if those items are not reflected in the said Annual Procurement Plan (APP), we cannot possibly process those requests and that's based on the Government Procurement Act, R. A. 9184. During the plotting of the Annual Procurement Plan (APP), the school administrators may invite a representative per grade level to solicit their innovative and realistic ideas regarding on what item are highly needed and most vital in their teaching – learning process. (2) The disbursing officers may innovate systematic procedures to fast tract the transactions to lessen the error during the preparation of the liquidation report. The Disbursing Officers may create an excel platform, a friendly - user template that can easily detect the errors particularly the balance checker upon the input of the amount in every disbursement voucher. (3) The disbursing officers may extend his or her time in giving relevant information, processes and procedures base on the new guidelines and advisories released by the division accounting department or from the Commission on Audit (COA). (4) Since there's no disruption of classes, there are times that the Canvassers and Purchasers cannot fulfill their duties and responsibilities as members of the Technical Working Group (TWG), one must take over in order to avoid the delay of the procurement process especially we can be able to meet the deadline in the submission of the liquidation report. The school administrators may assign a person who will canvass in case the Canvassers are not available. (5) For the future researchers to undertake similar researches to determine the challenges encountered and coping mechanisms of disbursing officers.

References

- Algorani, Emad B., Gupta Vikas (2022). Coping mechanisms. [Googlescholar.com](https://www.google.com)
- Ameriks, J., Caplin, A. Leahy, J. (2003). Atkinson, A., Messy, F. (2011). Assessing financial literacy in 12 countries.
- Austin, J. L. (1962), How to do things with words. <https://pure.mpg.de/>.
- Banks, J., Oldfield, Z. (2007). Understanding pensions: cognitive functions, numerical ability and retirement saving.
- Behrman, J., Mitchell, O. Soo, C., Bravo, D. (2010). Financial literacy, schooling, and wealth accumulation. <https://repository.upenn.edu/>.
- Buss, D., Greiling H. (2018). Adaptive individual differences.
- Butler, (1993), Derrida (1990). Performance theory.
- COA. (1997).COA Circular no. 97-002 Restatement with amendments of the rules and regulations on the granting, utilization and liquidation of cash advances provided for under COA Circular No. 90-331 dated May 3, 1990. coa.gov.ph.
- COA (1990). COA Circular No. 90-331 Rules and regulations on the granting, utilization and liquidation of cash advances. coa.gov.ph
- Cobry, S. (2014). Collaborative Theory.
- Cofer, C. N., Appley, M. H. (1964) Motivation.
- Crossman, A. (2019) The presentation of self in everyday life <https://www.Thought>.
- Daba, A. (2021). A Multidisciplinary peer reviewed Journal ISS no. 2581-4230 Volume 7, Issue 6. <https://www.researchgate.net/>.
- Deltiens, V. (2005). Transformation of the South African schooling system: The fault-lines in South African school governance: policy or people. Braamfontein:CEPD.
- DepEd Order no. 012 s. 2022, Policy guidelines for the provision of learning resources and needed devices and equipment and funding

- relevant activities for the implementation of basic education - learning continuity plan. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/>.
- DepEd Order No. 13 (2016) - Implementing guidelines on the direct release and use of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) allocations of schools, including other funds managed by schools. www.deped.gov.ph
- DepEd. (2001). Creating a BAC for Department of Education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph>.
- DepEd. (2016). Implementing guidelines on the direct release of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE). <https://www.deped.gov.ph>.
- Dewey, J. (1887). Learning by doing. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1979-27801-001> Education Act of 1982- Batas Pambansa BLG.232). www.chanrobles.com/bataspambansabilang232.html
- Fraleley, R. A. , Katz, Bill (2019). Finance, budget, and management for reference services. <https://books.google.com.ph/>.
- Gempes, G.P. (2014). Self-development beliefs and values of the workforce as constructs in the attainment of the firms' learning organization status. International proceedings of economics development and research, 70,121. <https://www.researchgate.net/>.
- Goffman, E. (1969). The presentation of the self in everyday life. <https://monoskop.org/>.
- Gould, S. (2018). Reflections on his view of life. <https://scholar.google.com>.
- Hernita, R., Arafat, Y., & Missriani (2020). The effect of work motivation, school culture, and school-based management on teacher's performance. Electronic research journal of social sciences and humanities. 2(2): 188-202. <http://www.eresearchjournal.com/>.
- Horvat, T. (2007). Leader accountability for school financial management. Presented during the 20th International Congress for Effectiveness and Improvement. <https://www.fm-kp.si/zalozba/>.
- Iidiko, R. (2014). Business economy / management, micro - economics, policy, planning, forecast and speculation, accounting - business administration. <https://www.cceol.com/>
- Iidiko, Rika C., Pete, Stefan, Vasile C. (2014). Traditional budgeting versus beyond budgeting; a literature review. <https://web.s.ebscohost.com/>.
- Katz, J. and Miller, F. (2023). Opening doors to teamwork and collaboration.
- Khattari, N. & Ling, C. & Jha, S. (2010). The effects of school -based management in the Philippines: An initial assessment using administrative data. <https://core.ac.uk/>.
- Latham, G. (2004). Work Motivation Theory and Research at the dawn of the twenty first century. www.2.rotman.utoronto.ca
- Lorico, A. (2016). Factors affecting the fiscal management practices of school administrators on MOOE in the city division of Borongan. Eastern Samar State University. Borongan City. <https://www.ijsid.com>.
- Lusardi, A. (2011). Americans' financial capability report prepared for the financial crisis Inquiry commission. <https://pensionresearchcouncil.wharton.upenn>.
- Mayor, J. (2019). Overcoming challenges in liquidation of MOOE of school heads in public schools. The freeman. April 5, 2019. <https://www.philstar.com/>.
- Mbwana, S. & Onyango, D. O. (2021). Perceived influence of final disbursement on school quality assurance in Nyamagana district, Tanzania: East African Journal of Education and Social Sciences. <https://eajess.ac.tz>.
- Mestry, R. 2006. The functions of school governing bodies in managing school finances. South African Journal of Education, 26 (1): 27-38. <https://eric.ed.gov/>.
- Ministry of Education of New Zealand (2020). Understanding school finances. available at accessed [06.10.20]. <https://www.educationallleaders.govt.nz/>.
- Miranda, Perez, David R. (2021). Disbursement and utilization of maintenance and other operating expenses (MOOE) practices of selected schools on the division of Palawan, Philippines. 2021//DOI;10.17605/OSF.10/95QG7.
- Moral, R. Jr. et al (2017). Document analysis of maintenance and other operating expenses (MOOE) of the elementary schools in the city division of Koronadal: A qualitative action research. <https://studylib.net/>.
- Morris, J. (2016). Advancing Collaboration theory. <https://books.google.ph>.
- Motowidlo, S. (2018). Job performance. <https://books.google.com.ph>.
- Pollastri, A. (2012). Collaborative problem solving approach: outcomes across settings

- Navarro, A. & Tanghal, A. (2017). The promises and pains in procurement reforms in the Philippines. <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph>.
- Ochada, N.R. & Gempes, G (2018). The realities of maintenance and other operating expenses (MOOE) allocation in basic education system: unheard voices of public school teachers. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*. 7(4): 315-324. 27)
- OECD/INFE International pilot exercise.
- Ogawa, R. (2016). The institutional sources of educational reform: The case of school-based management. *american educational research journal*. 31(3): 519-548. <https://www.ijstr.org/.Psycnet.Apa.OrgQuarterly> journal of economics. <https://academic.oup.com/qje>.
- Regalado, M. (2018). Gender ad civil status respondents. <https://books.google.ph>. Republic Act 9184. Government procurement reform act-https://www.gppb.gov.ph/assets/pdfs/Updated%202016%0IRR_31%20M Rules and regulations on the granting, utilization and liquidation of cash advances. https://www.coa.gov.ph/wpfd_file/coa-circular-no-90-331-may-3-1990/.
- Sonberg, M. (1998). Awareness intervention. Who needs it? [Googlescholar.com](https://scholar.google.com)

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lalaine D. Jacob

Iligan City Central District
Division of Iligan City – Philippines

Vilma H. Arazo, EdD

St. Peter’s College – Philippines